

CRUISE REPORT FARDWO-DS2

short version

RV Sarmiento de Gamboa

17/09/2024 Reykjavik (Iceland)
25/09/2024 Reykjavik (Iceland)

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

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1. Summary

The Denmark Strait (DS), situated between Iceland and Greenland, serves as a compelling study area for researchers in various fields of oceanography. This strait acts as a critical gateway, connecting the Arctic and Atlantic Oceans. Its unique geographic location and complex oceanographic dynamics make it an ideal location for investigating a wide range of phenomena related to ocean circulation and climate patterns. In DS the dense water being formed at the Nordic Seas, consisting of the Norwegian, Greenland, and Iceland Seas, overflows the strait's central sill and the East Greenland Shelf (EGS), eventually reaching the Irminger Basin in the North Atlantic Ocean. The Denmark Strait Overflow (DSO) is the main focus of the FAR-DWO DS2 cruise onboard RV Sarmiento de Gamboa (CSIC). This cruise follows FARDWO DS1 cruise that took place in July-August 2023.

Despite extensive studies on the DSO by the physical oceanography community, its sediment transport capacity and far-reaching effects on seafloor relief, as well as its signature in bottom water geochemistry and sedimentary records, remain largely unexplored. Furthermore, the effects of flow constriction caused by the DS sill and the complex topographic features in the EGS have received limited attention, despite their crucial role in understanding DSO dynamics and their significance in the broader ocean circulation system. To address these research gaps, the FAR-DWO DS2 cruise employed a combination of multidisciplinary observational analyses, sampling strategies and continuous monitoring of dense water overflows (DWOs). This report presents the technical aspects and the preliminary results of the cruise.

The scientific research conducted during the cruise has been made possible by the grant PID2020-114322RB-I00, funded by the Spanish MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033.

2. Goals of the cruise and methodological setup

The research objectives and the methodological setup of the cruise has consisted on:

- (i) the recovery of mooring lines deployed during the FARDWO-DS1 cruise to gain insights into the changing hydrography and sedimentation related to DWOs, covering one year.
- ii) the acquisition of CTD casts with LADCP and sADCP data to gather comprehensive data of the water masses within the Denmark Strait (DS) and the nearby region of the Kangerlussuaq Trough, allowing for an intricate analysis of the distribution and structure of the study area.
- (iii) the obtention of high-resolution bathymetric and very shallow seismic data to determine the physical imprint of DWOs on the seafloor and subseafloor in the DS sill and the Kangerlussuaq Trough Mouth Fan.

Furthermore, throughout the cruise we have conducted real-time analyses of both forecasted and hindcasted water mass behaviours using outputs from oceanic models. These insights proved immensely valuable in guiding the on-site decision-making process.

3. Participants and external collaborations

The FAR-DWO DS2 cruise onboard research team consisted of 18 scientists and 5 technicians from Spain, France, Iceland, Switzerland and Germany. Throughout the expedition, we received invaluable technical support from the Unidad de Tecnología Marina (UTM-CSIC).

Comprising the on-board team are:

Name	Surname	Organisation	Role
David	Amblas	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	Chief Scientist
Anna	Sanchez-Vidal	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	Chief Scientist
Antonio M.	Calafat Frau	University of Barcelona (Spain)	Scientist
Marc	Cerdà Domènech	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	Scientist
Helena	Fos Serdà	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	PhD Student
Luisa	Gonçalves de Freitas	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	PhD Student
Galderic	Lastras Membrive	Universitat de Barcelona (Spain)	Scientist
Maria Dolores	Pérez Hernández	Universidad Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	Scientist
Mara	Navarro Buigues	Universidad Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	PhD Student
Angel	Ruiz Angulo	University of Iceland (Iceland)	Scientist
Charly	de Marez	University of Iceland (Iceland)	Technician
Ronan	Apprioual	IFREMER (France)	Technician
Ricardo	Silva Jacinto	IFREMER (France)	Scientist
Andreas	Welsch	Hamburg University (Germany)	Technician
Chiara	Monforte	Hamburg University (Germany)	Technician
Núria	Casacuberta Arola	ETH – Zurich (Switzerland)	Scientist
Laia	Romero Gonzalez	Lobelia Earth (Spain)	Scientist
David	Fernandez Fontaiña	UTM - CSIC (Spain)	Technician
Joaquín	Salvador Castiella	UTM - CSIC (Spain)	Technician
Alberto	Arias Gonzalez-Anleo	UTM - CSIC (Spain)	Technician
José Alberto	Serrano Mayo	UTM - CSIC (Spain)	Technician
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Figure 1. Photography of the cruise FAR-DWO DS2 DS2 research team, technicians team, captain, officers and crew members.

4. Daily operations (narrative)

September 16, 2024:

Embarkment of all scientists. Security and informatics talk. Meeting with all people involved in mooring operations (UB, IFREMER, UH) with all officers, captain, and boatswain.

September 17, 2024:

Initiation of the survey, departing from the port of Reykjavik at 08:30, with navigation to the first CTD station, with relatively good weather. At 10:00, data recording initiated for the parasound system. At 13:00 ADCP data recording started. Following this, from 13:10 all systems are acquiring. We start working in 24h shifts. Good weather and northern lights in the evening.

September 18, 2024:

At 08:32 we perform a CTD at the mooring A site and at 10:00 we start triangulation and release of mooring A, that is successfully recovered at 12:23. We move to mooring B, that is released and successfully recovered at 14:40. Navigation to the first CTD station of the transect 1. CTD profiles in continuous mode. Good weather.

September 19, 2024:

CTD operations ongoing. At station CTD13 on its way up (16:49, 1933 m depth) we lose communication with the deck unit. Apparently, the deck unit was left on and something burned out. We recover the CTD. The repairing operations by UTM technicians last until 00:52 of the next day. Good weather and northern lights in the evening.

September 20, 2024:

Due to technical issues with the CTD we remain in stand by for a few hours and we decide to skip the entire transect T2 and start doing high-resolution bathymetric and very shallow seismic data in the sand waves area, on our way to transect T3. UTM technicians work intensively on the backup CTD all day long. We are back at CTD profiling at 01:49. Good weather.

September 21, 2024:

We stop the CTD transect T3 at 08:30 to recover mooring C (UH). After 1h trying to communicate we realize about bad coordinates (7 minutes). We move to the correct coordinates. At 10:15 the mooring is released and at 10:45 is onboard. We perform a CTD (CTD21) and redeploy the mooring again at 12:11. We continue with T3 and forget about starting ADCP for half of the transect. Transit to T4 during the night. Good weather and northern lights.

September 22, 2024:

We reach the beginning of T4 at 07:30 and start with CTD operations during all day, in front of Greenland. During T5 we also record EK80 data. Good weather and northern lights.

September 23, 2024:

CTD operations during all day. Good weather and northern lights.

5. Methodology and preliminary results**5.1. Lowered CTD****5.1.1. System and operations**

The CTD plan was designed aiming for three objectives: calibrating the mooring instruments, capturing the overflow current and characterizing the Kangerlussuaq Trough. During FARDWO-DS2 cruise we conducted 65 CTD stations using a SBE 9plus System. This CTD, equipped with different sensors (Table 1), was mounted on a rosette with a carousel of 24x12L Niskin bottles.

From station 00 to station 15 the CTD run on dual mode, the configuration file for these stations is called FARDWODS2.config. At station 15 the unit deck broke, and it had to be changed, as well as the pig tail of the CTD. After station 16 new dual sensors were used

Table 1. Serial number and calibration dates of all CTD sensors attached to the rosette, for stations 01 to 15.

Device	Type	SN and calibration date
Temperature	4669	06-Oct-21
Temperature 2	4659	18-Feb-21
Conductivity	3289	07-Oct.21
Conductivity 2	0852	16-Feb21
Pressure	0852	09-Nov-21
Oxygen	1980	25-Mar-23
Altimeter	40397	
Fluoremeter	3595	02-Nov.21
PAR	70160	17-May-2016
pH	382	16-Aug-16

Table 2. Serial number and calibration dates of all CTD sensors attached to the rosette, for stations 16 and beyond.

Device	Type	SN and calibration date
Temperature	4747	17-Mar-23
Temperature 2	5332	05-Sept.23
Conductivity	3361	21-Feb-23
Conductivity 2	3761	05-Sept-23
Pressure	0877	3-Apr-23
Oxygen	1665	28-Mar-23
Altimeter	40397	
Fluoremeter	6268	04-Jun-2020
PAR	70160	17-May-2016
pH	382	16-Aug-16

(Table 2). Hence from here on the stations used the configuration file FARDWODS2_mod2.config.

5.1.2. Preliminary results

The station 00 was carried out as a control cast before the cruise and to calibrate the moorings. The stations 01 to 15 composed Transect 1, located where the moorings deployed on FARDWO-DS1 lay. The vertical sections of potential temperature, salinity, density and geostrophic velocity are presented on Figure 3.

After doing the T1 we transit to T3, drawn as an extension of the MFRI standard section Látrabjarg. Figure 4 presents the vertical sections of this transect.

In addition, vertical sections of oxygen, fluorescence, turbidity and pH are presented for transect 1 (Figure 7).

Figure 2. θ -S diagram from all CTD stations: red (T1), blue (T3), green (T4), orange (T5), yellow (T6) and brown (Denmark Strait station). Black lines represent different isopycnals of neutral density.

Figure 3. Vertical sections for Transect 1 of (a) potential temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density and (d) geostrophic velocity. The geostrophic velocity is obtained from the wind thermal equation and with the reference layer at the isopycnal 27.8 kg/m³.

Figure 4. Vertical sections for Transect 3 of (a) potential temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density and (d) geostrophic velocity. The geostrophic velocity is obtained from the wind thermal equation and with the reference layer at the isopycnal 27.8 kg/m³.

5.2. Lowered Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (LADCP)

The LADCP data acquisition has been split in two periods. From station 1-15, two Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCP) were mounted on the CTD rosette to obtain full-depth horizontal current profiles at each hydrographic station (CTD/LADCP). The ADCP's used were 300 kHz Workhorse Monitor (Teledyne RD Instruments). The two ADCPs were configured to sample in master/slave mode to ensure synchronization. The master ADCP was the down-looker (serial number 15016) and the slave was the up-looker (SN: 24479). An external battery case supplied energy to both units. The second period of the cruise used only one single down-looker ADCP from station 17 onwards. The rest of the settings described below remained unchanged.

Communication with the instruments, start-and-stop data acquisition and data download were carried out by means of the BBTalk software, family of Teledyne toolboxes. The LADCP communications computer was synchronized with the ship server clock as well as the CTD computer to ensure both instruments had the same time stamps. The ADCP instruments clock were carefully reset for every single deploy avoiding internal clocks temporal drift. This practice improves a lot the solution, it is recommended to follow the same strict procedure for future LADCP/CTD deployments.

The vertical bin size was set to 8 m for both ADCPs. Single ping data were recorded in narrow bandwidth to increase range. Data was acquired in beam coordinates, with blank distance set to 8 m. More details about the configuration can be found in the scripts sent to the ADCPs before every cast, which were unaltered throughout the cruise and are shown as annexes.

LADCP processing was carried out with LDEO IX version 14 downloaded from Andreas Thurnherr github. Processing parameters were set in a `set_cast_params.m` script written for this cruise, which is included in the annexes. There are two variations of this file containing the parameters, mainly due to the change from dual ADCP, up-looker and down-looker, to single down-looker only. For all the stations the solution including bottom tracking has been implemented to perform the inversion. The velocity profiles included in this report do not include the SADCP data to constrain the solution. This will be performed as a future task, which will improve the solution of the velocity profiles. The caveats during post-processing include careful treatment of bottom detection as the LADCP was deployed at the same time as Topaz and multibeam, which induces acoustic contamination. This can be corrected by changing the bottom tracking parameters `p.btrk_ts` and `p.btrk_range`, see the parameter `set_cast_params.m` file for reference.

Only one station is missing LADCP data, station 15. Additionally, station 13 stopped far from the bottom as the CTD unit stopped recording and we recoiled back, and we need to analyze separately downcast-only. Station 21 had several stops during the downcast and needs additional treatment; however, this station is outside of the transects, which does not modify the figures presented below.

For all processed stations, the individual profiles summarized in folders within the LADCP/summary. The format for each station is `stXX`, where `XX` is the station number in `%02d` format, i.e., station 1 is `st01` and station 11 is `st11`; each folder contains the canonical 14 output figures resulting from the post-processing toolbox. The most relevant figure with the

velocity profiles is named following the format: `st_01.png`, where `st` is the station number.

The figures below show the across and along sections T1 and T3.

Selected LADCP stations

Figure 5. LADCP derived vertical velocity sections for the transect T1. Left: East-West component of the velocity and Right: North-West component.

Figure 6. LADCP derived vertical velocity sections for the transect T3. The velocities have been rotated to represent (left) across section and (right) along section.

5.3. Water sampling

5.3.1. Water sampling for radionuclide transient tracer

A total of 93 seawater samples were taken at 14 stations for the analysis of radionuclides transient tracers (^{129}I , ^{236}U) and 23 samples were collected for the further analysis of ^3H in 4 stations (see Table 1 for details). Figure 7 shows the location of these stations at each transect (including a profile that was taken on the transit back to Reykjavik (i.e. T2_01)). Water samples were collected directly from the 12L Niskin bottles and codes of each sample represent transect number (TX), station number at each transect (XX) and CTD bottle (XX). For example, a sample taken at Transect 1, station 5 and CTD bottle 20 has been coded as T1_05_20. The number of samples taken at each station goes from 4 to 9 (Table 3), and depths were chosen at each profile according to the different water masses observed during the CTD deployment.

For the analysis of ^{236}U , samples were collected in 3L plastic cubitainers and stored in carton boxes. Samples that will be analyzed for ^{129}I were taken in dark 250ml plastic bottles and stored in boxes. Finally, samples for the analysis of ^3H were collected in 1L plastic bottles (Figure 8). Seawater at station T2_01 was collected in 2x 1.5L drinking bottles (3L per depth), from which an aliquot of 250ml will need to be extracted for ^{129}I and the rest will be used for the analysis of ^{236}U . These have been marked as "(x)" in Table 3.

Figure 7. Stations sampled for radionuclides transient tracers at the different transects. T2_01 was a profile taken on the way back to Reykjavik.

Table 3. list of stations sampled for the analysis of radionuclides transient tracers, with each corresponding CTD numbers, the depths sampled and the information of which radionuclides will be analyzed from each station.

Station	CTD #	Depths (m)	3L for ^{236}U	0.25L for ^{129}I	1L for ^3H
T1_05	1	20, 100, 200, 350, 400, 650, 780	x	x	
T1_07	7	20, 100, 250, 450, 600, 750, 950, 1000, 1150	x	x	
T1_09	9	20, 200, 300, 600, 700, 1100, 1350, 1500	x	x	x
T1_10	10	300, 700, 800, 1100, 1350, 1550, 1650, 1720	x	x	
T3_04	20	5, 70, 200, 300, 400, 520, 580, 642	x	x	x
T3_06	22	15, 50, 80, 150, 250, 380, 400, 495	x	x	
T3_08	24	20, 100, 240, 340, 440, 482	x	x	
T3_10	26	20, 150, 240, 300, 374	x	x	
T4_05	34	20, 220, 400, 536	x	x	x (20 and 536m)
T5_05	47	20, 100, 220, 350, 470	x	x	x
T5_07	49	20, 110, 230, 400, 530	x	x	
T5_08	50	20, 110, 200, 300, 400, 447	x	x	
T6_06	60	30, 175, 350, 450, 512	x	x	
T2_01	65	50, 200, 400, 500, 600, 700, 750, 820, 868	(x)	(x)	

Figure 8. Picture of the three types of containers used to collect samples from each different radionuclide. On the left, a 3L cubitainer for the analysis of ^{236}U , in the middle a 1L bottle for the analysis of ^3H and on the right a 250ml dark bottle for the analysis of ^{129}I .

5.4. Moorings

During the previous FARDWO DS1 cruise in July-August 2023, 2 moorings were deployed and left for an entire year. The two moorings were successfully recovered during the FARDWO DS2 cruise on the 19 September 2024. In addition, during the cruise we recovered and redeployed a mooring of University of Hamburg. The following tables and figures include all information about mooring design and instrumentation, and some of the data downloaded (raw data). Data has not been interpreted.

Figure 9. Moorings A, B and C (UH-DS2) recovered (and redeployed in the case of UH-DS2) during the FARDWO DS2 cruise.

Table 4. Table with details of the mooring A.

Instrument	S/N	Details	Programming
Mooring FD DS A Deployed the 3/8/2023 11:42. Recovered the 18/09/2024 12:23. 65°14.6424'N; 31°19.0640'W; 1335 m			
Acoustic Release	AR8 2386	1BC9 + 1B49 (int) 1BC9 + 1B55 (rel)	
Single Point Currentmeter with Seapoint T002	3KL 5276		Measurement 600 sec Average interval 60 sec Start deployment 04/08/2023 00:00

Comments: the currentmeter recorded data until 26/4/2024, when battery voltage decreased below 8v and stopped. Battery calculator of the deployment planning function of the AQD software seems to not work in low temperatures (that interval was supposed to use 70% of the capacity).

SBE37	23176		Measurement 120 sec Start deployment 04/08/2023 00:00
The SBE37 was placed in the CTD rosette in CTD04 to 11 (measurement=120 sec), and CTD21 to CTD31 (measurement=10 sec) in order to calibrate/compare all instruments.			
Sediment trap	09-357		1 1/9/2023 00:00 2 1/10/2023 00:00 3 1/11/2023 00:00 4 1/12/2023 00:00 5 1/1/2024 00:00 6 1/2/2024 00:00 7 1/3/2024 00:00 8 28/7/2024 00:00 9 29/7/2024 00:00 10 30/7/2024 00:00 11 31/7/2024 00:00 (empty bottle) 12 1/7/2024 00:00 Close 2/7/2024 00:00

ADCP Teledyne (X2)	IFREMER		Data start 03/08/2023 12:00:00 Measurement frequency: 6 mins Depth cells: 4m Ping per ensemble: 11 Ping interval: 3sec Ambiguity velocity: 3m/s Blank: 1.76 m Magnetic variation: -17.4°
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Table 5. Table with details of the mooring B.

Instrument	S/N	Details	Programming
Mooring FD DS B Deployed 3/8/2023 9:43 Recovered the 18/09/2024 14:40. 65°01.610'N; 31°22.209'W; 1878 m			
Acoustic Release	AR8 3152	1C68 + 1C49 (int) 1C68 + 1C55 (rel)	
Single Point Currentmeter	3KL 5276		Measurement 600 sec Average interval 60 sec Start deployment 04/08/2023 00:00
Comments: the battery suffered from a leakage of acid that damaged the connection with the interface electronics. However, the interface seems ok. We couldn't download data, the currentmeter is shipped to Barcelona to see if we can get data out of the memory slot.			
Sediment trap	09-362		1 1/9/2023 00:00 2 1/10/2023 00:00 3 1/11/2023 00:00 4 1/12/2023 00:00 5 1/1/2024 00:00 6 1/2/2024 00:00 7 1/3/2024 00:00 8 28/7/2024 00:00 9 29/7/2024 00:00 10 30/7/2024 00:00 11 31/7/2024 00:00 12 1/7/2024 00:00 Close 2/7/2024 00:00
Start deployment 04/08/2023 00:00			

Sediment trap	09-357		1 1/9/2023 00:00 2 1/10/2023 00:00 3 1/11/2023 00:00 4 1/12/2023 00:00 5 1/1/2024 00:00 6 1/2/2024 00:00 7 1/3/2024 00:00 8 28/7/2024 00:00 9 29/7/2024 00:00 10 30/7/2024 00:00 11 31/7/2024 00:00 (empty bottle) 12 1/7/2024 00:00 Close 2/7/2024 00:00
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Table 6. Table with details of the mooring C.

Instrument	S/N	Details	Programming
Mooring DS2 UHH Deployed the 21/09/2024 12:10. 66°07.303'N; 27°16.832'W; 571 m			
Acoustic Release 1	679		
Acoustic Release 2	815		
SBE 37 Microcat SMP-ODO	37-26210		Start logging at 20 Sep 2024 16:00:00 Sample interval = 1800 seconds
SBE 37 Microcat SMP	37-26201		Start logging at 20 Sep 2024 16:00:00 Sample interval = 10 minutes
The two SBE37 were placed in the CTD rosette in CTD 11 (measurement=10 sec for SN 26201 and 20 sec for SN 26210), in order to calibrate/compare all instruments. The CTD rosette stopped for 10min at bottom depth, 600 and 300 m in order to allow for the microcat to equilibrate and get good reference data.			
ADCP Teledyne Workhorse 150 kHz 40" Float	24289		Deployment start 20/09/2024 18:00:00 Measurement frequency: 20 mins Depth cells: 8m Ping per ensemble: 50 Ping interval: 24sec Blanking distance: 12.21 m Magnetic variation: -15°

Mooring DS2 UHH Deployed 10/08/2023 11:44 Recovered 21/09/2024 10:45 66°07.28'N; 27°16.94'W; 571 m		
Acoustic Release Release 0855	1190	Arm 0878
SBE 37 Microcat SMP-ODO	37-13995	Start logging at 04 Aug 2023 00:00:00 Stop logging 21 Sept 2024 12:50 Sample interval = 1800 seconds
ADCP Teledyne Workhorse 74 kHz 40" Float	24917	Deployment start 10 Aug 2023 00:00:00 End of deployment 19 Mar 2024 23:58 Measurement frequency: 20 mins Depth cells: 8m (40 bins) Ping per ensemble: 12 Ping interval: 25 sec Blanking distance: 13.5 m Magnetic variation: -15.57°

The SBE 37 SN 13995 was placed on the CTD rosette at CTD60. Microcat data was set to record every 30s and we did 3 10min stops at 500m, 350m and 170m

Figure 10. Sediment trap sample cups.

5.4.1. Presentation of the data from the Ifremer's ADCPS

Position

The mooring deployed by Ifremer is documented in the FARDWO cruise report of 2023 (§6.4, pp 59-61). The mooring had been deployed 3rd of August 2023, at 11:42 am. The a priori deployment position is 65°14.6424' N ; 31°19.0640'W. This point is 1335 m deep. In 2024, before recovering the mooring a triangulation was made. The estimated mooring position is deviated 223 m from the target position.

The triangulation was done using the following points:

Points	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)	Distance (m)
Deployment	65°14.6424'	31°19.0640'	223
Used for triangulation	65°15.6530'	31°19.0725'	2273
Used for triangulation	65°14.0229'	31°17.2756'	2484
Used for triangulation	65°14.0512'	31°20.9853'	2293
Estimated position	65°14.7094'	31°19.3036'	---

Mooring behaviour

Before any further analysis it is important to understand the behaviour of the buoy housing the two 300 kHz ADCPs. The buoy is connected to the anchor by a 100 m long line and hence relatively free to move up and down with the strong currents.

Figure 11. Vertical position of the buoy based on the pressure gauge of the 300 kHz ADCP looking down. High-frequency data (6 min) is shown with filtered data (red, 10 days).

The vertical displacement of the buoy is important. The mean position is around 20 m deeper than the rest position. Standard oscillations around this mean value is 12 m. Low frequency oscillations show that the buoy is also responding to the flow and not only driven by high behaviour.

This “low-frequency” adaptation to the flows may be seen in the behaviour of the buoy. The

histograms of the pitch and roll behaviour, together with the ADCPs heading show relatively stable behaviour considering the strong vertical displacement under current entrainment.

Figure 12. Heading, Pitch and roll behaviours of the ADCP looking down

Figure 13. Heading, Pitch and roll behaviours of the ADCP looking up

Environmental data

Environmental data (e.g. temperature, salinity, turbidity) is acquired by the Aquadop installed 23 m above the sea bed. At the level of the ADCPs only temperature is recorded. Both ADCPs measured temperature. The instruments show a good agreement.

The recorded temperature is modulated by the vertical movement of the buoy. Some analysis is needed to separate the changes in temperature due to the vertical displacement of the buoy from the natural temperature variability.

Velocity data

The velocity data shows very weak vertical structure. Both amplitude and direction present small differences in vertical. More detailed analyses is needed to correct the vertical displacement of the buoy. The full analysis of the currents must consider the strong vertical displacement of the buoy.

Figure 14. Raw data from WinADCP software. Top figure is the ADCP looking upwards. The bottom figure is from the ADCP looking downwards. Data was acquired from 03/08/2023 to 17/09/2024. The impact of the vertical movement is strong on both ADCPs. The vertical homogeneity of the currents can be observed in and between both data sets.

6.5. Acoustic echosounders

5.5. Hull-mounted acoustic echosounders

5.5.1. Vessel-mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (sADCP)

There was one Vessel-Mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (VM-ADCP, also referred to as ship-ADCP or sADCP) installed and operational on R/V Sarmiento de Gamboa to collect velocity profiles below the ship. The ADCPs, model Ocean Surveyor (TRDI, USA) 75 kHz installed in the port retractable keel below the vessels' hull. The ADCPs worked in narrowband mode to maximize range.

Data was acquired and pre-processed with the VmDas software ver. 1.50.19. This program continuously collects ADCP single ping data and merges it with navigation and attitude data from the ship's instruments. The files generated by VmDas are saved in the local hard disks of respective PCs devoted to this task. Every 12h the files also transferred to a read-only folder in the ship network. Most of the parameters are adjusted through the ADCP configuration file, while communications (ADCP, NMEA) are tuned in a separate menu. The ship's velocity (necessary to obtain absolute, current velocities) is monitored by both navigation (gyro/GPS) and bottom track (ADCP) data, the latter being restricted to the ADCP's range. VmDas rotates, references and averages the raw single-ping data, while applying quality control thresholds, and finally outputs STA (short term averages) and LTA (long term averages) files, which in this survey were set to 2 and 10 minutes averages respectively. These STA/LTA files were inspected with the WinADCP software during navigation to check acoustic and diagnostic data as well as preliminary current velocities. The follow up of the postprocessing will be continued on land.

The sADCP was turned off during the recovery and deployment of the mooring in transect 3. There is a gap on the data during 21/9/2024 (from 11:46 to 23:31). After that pause, the data

5.5.2. Multibeam bathymetry

Bathymetry has been acquired using a hull-mounted Atlas Hydrosweep DS-3 multibeam echosounder. This model has a working frequency of 15.5 kHz (emission frequency between 14.5 and 16.0 kHz) and a full ocean depth range, creating 320 beams with a 1°x1° beam opening. The typical range achieved at 700 m water depth is approximately 3000 m (4.2 times water depth), with an accuracy of 0.2% water depth. Beam forming mode selected has been equidistant throughout the cruise, with a swath opening of between 100 and 120°. Data have been acquired during transits between stations at a variable speed of 8-11 kt using the Teledyne PDS Suite (Acquisition, Figure 15; and Reson Sonar UI, Figure 16) and recorded in s7k format for an easy import to Caris HIPS & SIPS. Data acquisition has been continuous during all operations, except during mooring retrieval due to interferences with mooring acoustic interrogation and release.

Linear distance of multibeam acquisition during transits sums up **1559.7 km** (Figure 17).

Multibeam data in s7K were imported to Caris HIPS & SIPS. A preliminary data processing was conducted onboard, with manual flagging of spurious soundings. The backscatter signal was not evaluated.

Figure 15. General view of the Teledyne PDS Acquisition window.

5.5.3. Very-high resolution profiles (TOPAS echosounder)

Very-high resolution seismic profiles were acquired using a hull-mounted Simrad TOPAS PS18 parametric source sub-bottom profiler. Transmitter was operated in normal mode, generating a chirp (HFM) pulse with a start frequency of 2 kHz, a stop frequency of 5 kHz and a chirp length of 100 ms. HRP stabilization was used, and beam control was set to auto. Ping interval was selected manually between 1000 and 1300 ms (Figure 18) so the multiple signal did not interfere with the bottom signal. Output level remained unchanged at 100%. Delay time was automatically changed with bottom tracking. The delay is saved in bit 109 of the SEG Y file. Trace length was set to 200 ms throughout the survey.

Real-time processing of the data consisted on a matched filter and gain control. A fixed continuous gain in the processing tab was added when judged necessary. Time variable gain was set manually and changed during the survey to improve the signal/noise ration into the deepest reflections. The start of the application of the TVG was locked to the bottom tracker (automatic with a threshold of 70-60% in a searching window of 10 ms of the highest amplitude).

The data generated by the TOPAS PS 18 profiler was logged both in the TOPAS raw data format (RAW) and SEG Y format. Raw data files of non-processed data are saved in the TOPAS format and can be later imported into the TOPAS software for reprocessing. SEG Y files record the real time processed data, and allow additional post-processing by any other seismic data processing software. RAW and SEG Y files include whole transects as well as stations. Each file includes 120 minutes of recording with a maximum file size of 100 Mb.

Figure 16. General view of the Teledyne RESON Sonar UI window with the selected acquisition parameters displayed below in the advanced tab.

Figure 17. General map of all multibeam data acquired in FARDWO-DS2.

Figure 18. General view of the TOPAS acquisition and processing software with transmission settings shown.

5.6. Thermosalinograph

5.6.1. TSG specifications

The RV Sarmiento de Gamboa is equipped with a thermosalinograph (TSG) that measures temperature and salinity from the seawater intake in the interior of the ship. The system was operated by the Unidad de Tecnología Marina (UTM) and consists of a Sea-Bird Electronics (SBE) 21. The accuracy of the temperature sensor is 0.001 °C, the resolution is 10⁻⁴ °C, and the response time is 0.065±0.01 s (Table 1). About the salinity sensor, it has a measurement range from 0.0 to 7.0 S/m with an accuracy of ±0.0003 S/m and a response time of 0.06 s (Table 2). The sampling frequency of the TSG is one measurement per 6 s. The cruise started with a TSG (Serial No. 3281), which was calibrated on 14/05/2024 by Sea-Bird GmbH.

5.6.2. Preliminary Results

Table 7. Specifications of temperature sensor SBE21

Calibration date	14 May 2024
Measurement range	-5 to +35°C
Accuracy	±0.001°C
Stability	Must demonstrate <0.001°C drift during the 6 months prior to delivery
Resolution	0.0003°C at 24 samples/s
Response time	0.065s ± 0.01 s (1.0 m/s water velocity)
Self-heating error	<0.0001°C in still water
Settling time	<0.5s to within 0.001°C

Table 8. Specifications of salinity sensor SBE21

Calibration date	14 May 2024
Measurement range	0.0 to 7.0 S/m
Accuracy	±0.0003 S/m
Stability	0.0003 S/m per month
Resolution	0.00004 S/m at 24 samples/s
Response time	0.060 s (pumped)
Settling time	<0.7 s to within 0.0001 S/m

5.7. Ocean forecast models from CMEMS

On the 16th of September, the day before the start of the cruise, we downloaded the forecast for the next 10 days: 16-25 September.

The model product, called Global Physics Analysis and Forecast is available free at Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS):

ID: GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016>

This has a regular longitude-latitude equirectangular projection, a horizontal grid width of 1/12 ~ 8km of horizontal resolution approximately, and 50 vertical levels, covering the whole globe. The variables and datasets downloaded are daily mean values, in the table below.

Table 9. Global Physics Analysis and Forecast datasets.

Name of variable	Abbreviation	Units	DatasetID
Eastward velocity	uo	m/s	cmems_mod_glo_phy-cur_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m
Northward velocity	vo	m/s	cmems_mod_glo_phy-cur_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m
Potential temperature	thetao	°C	cmems_mod_glo_phy-thetao_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m
Salinity	so	psu	cmems_mod_glo_phy-so_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m

During the FARDWO-DS2 cruise, we created some figures with this forecast data to illustrate the path of the Denmark Strait Overflow (sigma potential density between 27.7 and 28 kg/m³) and its temporal variability during the cruise.

FAR-DWO

FAR, reaching impacts
of Dense Water Overflows
in the North Atlantic
and the Mediterranean

